

Some β -Phenethylamine Derivatives. Part II

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Several substituted β -phenethylamines have been synthesised by the lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the corresponding β -nitrostyrenes, the latter being obtained from the appropriate aldehydes.

β -Phenethylamines are well known for their sympathomimetic activity, which is modified by the presence of substituents both in the side chain as well in the aromatic nucleus¹. With a view to studying the effects on the physiological activity of different substituent groups, like alkyl and alkoxy, in various positions in the nucleus, several β -phenethylamines were prepared².

These amines were synthesised by the condensation of aldehydes (Table I) with nitromethane in acetic acid solution³ to yield the corresponding β -nitrostyrenes. The latter were then reduced with lithium aluminium hydride⁴ to the β -phenethylamine derivatives (Table II).

The aldehydes listed in Table I are hitherto unknown. Compounds (I to XI) were prepared by alkylation of the corresponding known hydroxybenzaldehydes with methyl or ethyl iodide in acetone solution in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate.

TABLE I

No.	Benzaldehyde.	M.P.	A l d e h y d e s.		2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones.		M.P.	% Nitrogen.	
			% Carbon.	% Hydrogen.	% Carbon.	% Hydrogen.		Found.	Reqd.
I	2,4-Dimethoxy-5-ethyl	92-93°	68.0	68.0	7.2	7.2	-	-	-
II	2,4-Diethoxy-5-ethyl	72-73°	70.5	70.2	8.1	8.1	-	-	-
III	2,4-Dimethoxy-5-propyl	82-83°	69.3	69.2	7.8	7.6	-	-	-
IV	2,4-Diethoxy-5-propyl	79-80°	71.3	71.1	8.4	8.4	-	-	-
V	2,4-Dimethoxy-5-hexyl	Oil	-	-	-	-	168-67°	12.9	13.0
VI	2,4-Diethoxy-5-hexyl	"	-	-	-	-	189-90°	12.1	12.2
VII	3,6-Dimethyl-4-methoxy	"	-	-	-	-	265-66°	16.4	16.2
VIII	3,6-Dimethyl-4-ethoxy	"	-	-	-	-	248-49°	15.8	15.6
IX	2,3-Dimethyl-4-methoxy	"	-	-	-	-	246-47°	16.4	16.2
X	2,3-Dimethyl-4-ethoxy	"	-	-	-	-	211-12°	15.7	15.6
XI	2,4,6-Trimethyl-3-methoxy	"	-	-	-	-	189-90°	15.4	15.6
XII	2,4-Dimethyl-3-hydroxy	"	-	-	-	-	234-35°	16.7	16.9
XIII	2,4-Dimethyl-3-methoxy	"	-	-	-	-	221-22°	16.3	16.2
XIV	2,4-Dimethyl-3-ethoxy	"	-	-	-	-	238-39°	15.9	15.6
XV	3,4-Dimethyl-2-hydroxy	"	-	-	-	-	274-75°	16.6	16.9
XVI	3,4-Dimethyl-2-methoxy	"	-	-	-	-	198-99°	15.9	16.2
XVII	3,4-Dimethyl-2-ethoxy	"	-	-	-	-	171-72°	15.9	15.6

*Also prepared by Kachru & Kachru (this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 311).

1. Burger, "Medicinal Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1951, Vol. I, p. 335.
2. Merchant and Mountwala, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 1774.
3. Gairud and Lappin, *ibid.*, 1953, **18**, 1.
4. Erne and Ramirez, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1950, **33**, 912; Ramirez and Burger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2782.

TABLE II
 β -Nitrostyrene. β -Phenethylamine picrate.

No	Substance	M. P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		M. P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
I	5-Ethyl-2-methoxy	Oil	$C_{11}H_{15}O_3N$	-	-	178-79°	$C_{17}H_{20}O_6N_4$	13.8	13.7
II	5-Ethyl-4-methoxy*	43-44°	$C_{11}H_{15}O_3N$	6.9	6.7	190-91°	$C_{17}H_{20}O_6N_4$	13.8	13.7
III	2,4-Dimethoxy-5-ethyl*	115-16°	$C_{12}H_{15}O_4N$	6.2	5.9	209-10°	$C_{18}H_{22}O_6N_4$	12.9	12.7
IV	2,4-Diethoxy-5-ethyl	108-109°	$C_{14}H_{19}O_4N$	5.2	5.2	191-92°	$C_{20}H_{26}O_6N_4$	12.0	12.0
V	2,4-Dimethoxy-5-propyl	100-101°	$C_{13}H_{17}O_4N$	5.8	5.5	190-91°	$C_{19}H_{24}O_6N_4$	12.0	12.3
VI	2,4-Diethoxy-5-propyl	98-99°	$C_{15}H_{21}O_4N$	5.3	5.0	182-83°	$C_{21}H_{28}O_6N_4$	11.8	11.7
VII	2,4-Dimethoxy-5-hexyl	67-68°	$C_{16}H_{23}O_4N$	5.0	4.7	134-35°	$C_{22}H_{30}O_6N_4$	11.3	11.3
VIII	2,4-Diethoxy-5-hexyl	79-80°	$C_{18}H_{27}O_4N$	4.8	4.4	182-83°	$C_{24}H_{34}O_6N_4$	10.5	10.7
IX	3,5-Dimethyl-4-methoxy	76-79°	$C_{11}H_{15}O_3N$	6.6	6.3	186-90°	$C_{17}H_{20}O_6N_4$	14.1	13.7
X	3,5-Dimethyl-4-ethoxy	Oil	$C_{12}H_{15}O_3N$	-	-	197-98°	$C_{18}H_{22}O_6N_4$	13.1	13.2
XI	3,6-Dimethyl-4-methoxy	127-28°	$C_{11}H_{15}O_3N$	6.6	6.8	178-79°	$C_{17}H_{20}O_6N_4$	13.4	13.7
XII	3,6-Dimethyl-4-ethoxy	141-42°	$C_{12}H_{15}O_3N$	6.7	6.3	172-73°	$C_{18}H_{22}O_6N_4$	13.3	13.2
XIII	2,3-Dimethyl-4-methoxy	98-99°	$C_{11}H_{15}O_3N$	6.5	6.3	184-85°	$C_{17}H_{20}O_6N_4$	13.4	13.7
XIV	2,3-Dimethyl-4-ethoxy	132-33°	$C_{12}H_{15}O_3N$	6.5	6.3	206-201°	$C_{18}H_{22}O_6N_4$	13.4	13.2
XV	2,4,6-Trimethyl-3-methoxy	Oil	$C_{12}H_{15}O_3N$	-	-	232-33°	$C_{18}H_{22}O_6N_4$	13.4	13.2
XVI	3,5-Dimethoxy	94-95°	$C_{10}H_{11}O_4N$	6.3	6.7	**191-92°	$C_{16}H_{19}O_6N_4$	13.6	13.6

* Also prepared by Kasbru *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 123; 1959, 36, 311.

** Djerard *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, 21, 976) recorded m.p. 217-18° for the picrate.

(Found: C, 47.3; H, 4.6; N, 13.6. $C_{16}H_{19}O_6N_4$ requires C, 46.9; H, 4.3; N, 13.6%).

2,4-Dimethyl-3-hydroxybenzaldehyde (XII) was synthesised by the Gattermann reaction on 2,6-xylen-1-ol, when along with the known 3,5-dimethyl-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde⁵ (XII) was also formed in small amounts, the two compounds being separated by steam distillation.

Similarly, the Gattermann reaction on 2,3-xylen-1-ol also afforded a mixture of the known 2,3-dimethyl-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 3,4-dimethyl-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (XV), which were separated by steam distillation. The position of the formyl group in (XV) was proved by its oxidation to the unknown 3,4-dimethyl 2-hydroxybenzoic acid; the other isomeric benzoic acid, namely, 3,4-dimethyl-5-hydroxy, being known.⁶

EXPERIMENTAL

β -Nitrostyrenes.—A mixture of the aldehyde (5 g.), nitromethane (5 ml), ammonium acetate (2 g.), and glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed at 130° for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid separating was collected and crystallised from methanol or acetic acid. If no solid separated, the resulting solution was poured into ice-water and the precipitated semisolid mass or oil was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried, and the solvent distilled when either a solid or an oil was left behind. The solid was purified by crystallisation, whereas the oil was directly treated for reduction.

β -Phenethylamines.—The reduction of the β -nitrostyrene with lithium aluminium hydride to the corresponding β -phenethylamine was carried out according to the general method followed by Erne and Ramirez⁴.

A solution of the β -nitrostyrene (3 g.) in dry ether (30 ml) was added dropwise to a well-stirred suspension of LiAlH₄ (2 g.) in dry ether (10 ml). A mixture of ether and benzene was employed for styrenes which were sparingly soluble in ether. The reaction mixture was gently refluxed for 2 hours and then decomposed with ice-cold water (180 ml). The reaction mixture was filtered and the ethereal layer was separated from the aqueous layer. On removal of ether, an oily residue was obtained which dissolved in ethanol. This solution was added to a hot ethanolic solution of picric acid. On cooling, yellow or orange crystals of the amine picrate were obtained which crystallised from ethanol or a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum ether (40-60°); yield about 60%.

Alkylation of Hydroxybenzaldehydes.—A mixture of aldehyde (5 g.), potassium carbonate (anhyd., 10 g.), methyl or ethyl iodide (5 ml), and dry acetone (100 ml) was refluxed for about 20 hours. Filtration and removal of acetone gave an oil which was taken in ether, washed with 2% sodium hydroxide, and then with water. Removal of the solvent yielded the alkylated aldehyde as a low melting solid or an oil; yield 80-85%.

3,4-Dimethyl-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde.—To a mixture of 2,3-xylen-1-ol (20 g.), zinc cyanide (30 g.), and dry thiophene-free benzene (250 ml), taken in a three-necked flask fitted with a mercury seal stirrer and a reflux condenser, cooled in an ice bath, was

5. Gattermann, *Annalen*, 1907, 357, 323.

6. Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 187.

passed dry HCl gas for 30 minutes. Powdered AlCl_3 (anhyd., 60 g.) was then added and the passage of HCl was continued. After 30 minutes, temperature was raised to 55° which was maintained for 6 to 7 hours, stirring and the passage of HCl being continued all the time. The solid separating was filtered and washed with benzene to remove any unchanged original compound. It was then added to water (200 ml) and subjected to steam distillation. The distilled product was salted out and extracted twice with ether. Removal of ether left the aldehyde as a colorless oil. Its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in red plates, m.p. $274-75^\circ$. (Found: N, 16.6. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N}_4$ requires N, 16.9%). It was assigned the structure, 3,4-dimethyl-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde after its oxidation to 3,4-dimethyl-2-hydroxybenzoic acid (yield 7 g.).

The residue after steam distillation was crystallised from toluene to give the known 2,3-dimethyl-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, m.p. $171-72^\circ$, yield 10 g. The aldehyde was prepared by Gattermann⁵ using hydrogen cyanide.

3,4-Dimethyl-2-hydroxybenzoic Acid.—To an aqueous solution of NaOH (1.53 g. in 12.1 ml water) was added 3,4-dimethyl-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1 g.) with vigorous stirring. Temperature of the mixture was at that point about 55° . With continued agitation, a solution of silver nitrate (1.02 g.) in water (4.55 ml), previously warmed to 55° , was added⁷. After about 5 minutes, the reaction mixture was filtered hot and washed with water. The alkaline filtrate was acidified with SO_2 and after cooling, the white precipitate was filtered, washed with water, and dried. The crude product on sublimation gave white plates of 3,4-dimethyl-2-hydroxybenzoic acid, m.p. $190-91^\circ$, yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 65.3; H, 6.2. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 65.0; H, 6.0%).

3,5-Dimethyl-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde.—A mixture of 2,6-xylene-1-ol (20 g.), zinc cyanide (30 g.), AlCl_3 (anhyd., 60 g.), and dry benzene (200 ml) was subjected to Gattermann's aldehyde synthesis, modified by Adams according to the procedure described for (XV). The unknown isomer, 3,5-dimethyl-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, was obtained from the steam-distilled product as a colorless oil (6 g.). Its 2,4-DNP crystallised from acetic acid in reddish plates, m.p. $234-35^\circ$. (Found: N, 16.7. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N}_4$ requires N, 16.9%). The known 3,5-dimethyl-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde was obtained from the residue after steam distillation. It crystallised from dilute ethanol in brown crystals, m.p. $114-15^\circ$, yield 9 g. The aldehyde was prepared by Gattermann using hydrogen cyanide.

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